

Eemotherapy Physics

Mohammed Ashfaq Hassan
M.D. CIMBENS

Abstract:- Emotherapy Physics: I go further to state that 3 and 6 are resolvers and are noble, 9 stays as stable and power. 1 does not exist though it exists in the form of Digital Support along with 0. Hence the weight or mass can be axed from element by conservation of energy in the form of frequency which can be charged negative or positive by a process of conservation intensity can be set by mixing module.

And hence represent Electric Current, on and off digital condition. Now it comes to payload-module.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the help of single digit number system we will resolve the mystery of mixing of periodic table and understand the atomic weight representation in order to set frequency, polarity and intensity.

That is diseases treatment module to be in digital format we need to set the TCP/IP bus. Thus what and all we see that exist on the earth is due to sand so we took the fertilizer module on which the plant exist and hence we have set the bus as 16 bit and finalize the 16th element and conserved using conservation of energy, which helps in communicating the body to identify the location of the disease and use molecular module to attack the disease and destroy them.

TCP/IP Concept: $3 = 2, 2, 2 = 2^1, 2^2, 2^3 = 2, 4, 8$

Similarly $6 = 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64 = 111111$

Similarly $9 = 111111111$

9 represent high powers 3 and 6 are noble.

Hence the new circular liquid digital charge came up bringing liquid digital medicine and safe to use without side effects as a proof.

B. Disease Treatment base is prepared with periodic table.

BA. The 3 and 6 mystery to resolve we need to apply molecule module.

II. METHOD

Atomic mass contains energy, charge, hence it has all the features covered under conservation of energy therefore we need to convert the periodic table elements Atomic mass into single digit by using single digit rule.

So Periodic Table

No. 1 is Hydrogen with mass 1.0078 is add up which is equal to 7 similar

No. 2 is Helium with weight 4.0026 equal to 3

No. 3 is Lithium with weight 6.938 equal to 8

No. 4 is Beryllium with weight 9.0122 equal to 5

No. 5 is Boron with weight 10.806 equal to 6

No. 6 is Carbon with weight 12.009 equal to 3

No. 7 is Nitrogen with weight 14.006 equal to 2

No. 8 is Oxygen with weight 15.999 equal to 6

No. 9 is Fluorine = 8

Single digit periodic table (SPT) came into existence.

Therefore single digit circular figure (CSD) is prepared having zero (0) at the center and 1 to 9 digits in circular and is based on atomic weight.

Fig. 1: (CSD)

The reason to put zero (0) in middle is it is a concept to change-over. And change-over can be a form of energy without a mass or weight but it has an identity, which can be reconverted and stored in mass with same features by the conservation of energy law.

➤ *Molecule Module:*

So as per molecule module (a) Odd force issue, (b) Even force issue and (c) Other issue.

- **On the left half:** 7, 5, 8, 6 exist

7	5	8		6
19 Potassium	22 Titanium	41 Niobium		8 Oxygen

And based upon the above module 7 and 5 cannot be mixed unless 8 and 6 helps.

3	6	9
2 Helium	18 Argon	13 Aluminum

Hence 3, 6 are noble and 9 are stable. Atomic number also represents Photon and generates magnetism, and atomic mass or weight represents energy, electricity and hence the force of gravity acts upon the mass.

- **Left with the right half:** 2, 3, 4, 1 exist

2	3	4		1
23 Vanadium	24 Chromium	11 Sodium		20 Calcium
7	2	3		4
1 Hydrogen	23 Vanadium	24 Chromium	11 Sodium	20 Calcium

Therefore 3 and 6 are noble 7 are not merge able unless high forces are applied, since left is odd and right is even and leads to formation of new (energy circular module) Figure (EOF) where EOF stand for even odd force – circle))

Fig. 2: EOF

BB. Method: Disease and medicine preparation

The body is a big world and identifying the location of disease you need some mechanism. Hence we have to take mathematic rule and understand the number system rule in periodic table with (single digit of periodic table).

Mathematic Addition Rule:

BBA) Even force adds with even force = 2 even force

BBB) Odd force adds with odd force = 2 odd force

BBC) Odd force with even force = neutral or lower force.

As per metadata the complete world exists on forces through conservation of energy rule. Hence this part helps in selection of elements from periodic table. And hence it's a liquid digital medicine physics.

Liquid digital medicine contains electric current have electrons and protons, negative charge flows and blowout, positive charge blowout and generates electromagnetic effects and is the energy, during preparation/after injecting smash withdraw smash excites to higher energy level, during preparation to identify or after injecting body identify the location of disease, and during conservation electromagnetic effects while equalizing makes the movement and pushes to higher energy state. Therefore

And molecular interaction (Covalent bonds) hold bonds intact and unchanged binary format of TCP/IP On and off or 1 and 0 is

Where 1 is electron negative charge and

0 is proton positive charge which doesn't flows

Human body and elements: Standard elements on earth, healthy humans have 1.2 volts therefore $1.2 = 3$

III. CONCLUSION

- 9 and 0 represent "Electrical Energy" and acts as start or glow and generates magnetism.
- 1 represent the "Electricity" and acts as flow representing power.
- Altogether 9 and 0 and 1 are parts of the electric current that is
- (Electric current = electricity and electrical energy)
- That even numbers is even forces and odd numbers are odd forces acts as payloads of electric current, to resolve and the vise-versa "issues"

CIMBENS has developed Eemotherapy or also called emergency medical preparation technique to combat at the horrific juncture of mass Human death due to non-availability of quick responsive medicine before 10-20 minutes in order to deal the emergency situation so that the patients can be saved from the serious and critical conditions that can occur if it's not treated instantly this technique can also be called as Digital Medicine preparation technique.

The special features of this technique is that it reduces the long terms animal based studies followed by clinical trials to short clinical trials and bypass animal studies and help to bring up scientific provable lab testable, easily merge able and manageable medicine in shortest time, and act to barricade before a pandemic or epidemic occurs.

This technology provides high sophisticated guidelines to all medical systems to plan the research based on the MBBS mode of disease identification hence can be used MBBS Doctors too,

- It's a mandatory guide lines for future generation of researcher's.
- Its needs the education of 5 major theories and 11 sub theories.
- Its needs the perfect understanding of atomic weight of elements of periodic table.
- Its needs through understanding of metadata.
- They are different ways or options available to researcher for preparing the medicine as its indigenous periodic table based.
- It's mandatory and a puzzle to transform the energy into digital energy with respect to "disease and its action, and the brain digital control system" through different modes.
- It's based on 16 bit bus similar to computer digital technology and uses ports base communication similar for whatsapp, yahoo, Skype.
- Developed anti-blockage and anti-thrombosis emergency treatment medicine.
- Its complex in nature and involves 10 system of education (list of educations)

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